

Impact of Open Inquiry Instructional Strategy on Secondary School Chemistry Students' Academic Achievement: A Student-Centred Approach Leveraging Digital Resources

Dr. OJO Omolabake Temilade¹ & TIJANI Bamidele Emmanuel²

¹Department of Science and Technology Education,
University of Lagos, Akoka, Yaba, Lagos State, Nigeria

²Department of Science Education,
University of Lagos, Akoka, Yaba, Lagos State, Nigeria

*Email: ¹otojo@unilag.edu.ng, ²tijaniemmanuelb@gmail.com

ORCID ID: ¹<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8744-3490>, ²<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-3466-4140>

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Abstract

The limitations of traditional teacher-centred instructional methods, such as the demonstration method, have led to a growing interest in student-centred approaches like open inquiry. Open inquiry emphasises active engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving by allowing students to independently explore learning materials and leverage digital resources such as online videos, simulations and virtual tools for learning. This study investigated the impact of the open inquiry instructional strategy on the academic achievement of secondary school chemistry students compared to the demonstration method. A pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental design was employed, involving 322 students from the intact classes of six purposively selected schools in Osun East Senatorial District, Nigeria. Students were assigned to experimental and control groups: the experimental group was taught using the Open Inquiry Instructional Guide (OIIG), while the control group was taught with the Demonstration Instructional Guide (DIG). Pre- and post-tests were conducted using a validated Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) to measure the effectiveness of both strategies. Data were analysed using ANCOVA and Two-Way ANOVA to evaluate differences in academic achievement and interaction effects based on school type. Results revealed that students taught using open inquiry significantly outperformed those taught with the demonstration method. While private school students achieved higher overall scores, the effectiveness of open inquiry was consistent across public and private schools. The findings highlight the potential of open inquiry to transform science education by fostering student autonomy and improving students' academic achievement, particularly when digital resources are effectively integrated. Schools, especially in resource-limited settings, are encouraged to adopt open inquiry as an instructional strategy while investing in teacher training and infrastructure to optimise its implementation. Further research is recommended to explore its long-term impact across other subjects and broader educational contexts.

Keywords: Open Inquiry, Academic Achievement, Student-Centered Learning, Chemistry Education.

Introduction

The increasing integration of digital tools in education has led to the rise of distinct student-centred learning approaches such as open inquiry, guided inquiry, blended classroom etc. Open inquiry emphasises complete student autonomy, guided inquiry involves teacher-facilitated exploration and blended classrooms combine digital tools with traditional learning methods to enhance student

engagement and understanding. These approaches encourage active participation and engagement in learning and have become increasingly prevalent in the 21st century's evolution of instructional strategies. Traditional teaching methods, such as the conventional lecture method, which primarily involves delivering information verbally to large audiences with limited interaction; the demonstration method, where the teacher performs experiments or scientific procedures while guiding students to replicate the processes themselves; and direct instruction, which involves a structured approach focusing on step-by-step teaching with ongoing assessment and feedback to ensure comprehension, are characterised by planned lectures and laboratory exercises where the teacher controls the flow of knowledge with minimal student participation.

These approaches have been criticised for not giving students the chance to interact thoroughly with content, which frequently leads to rote memorisation rather than deep comprehension and application (Annisa & Rohaeti, 2018). Furthermore, traditional teaching methods are increasingly viewed as insufficient in providing students with the skills required for scientific inquiry and innovation, as science education places a strong emphasis on the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Research has indicated that although traditional approaches can successfully communicate information, they cannot develop the critical thinking and application abilities required in modern scientific settings (Anil, 2023).

Open inquiry provides promising solutions to these deficiencies of the traditional teaching approaches by allowing students to independently explore learning materials and engage in their learning process by using websites, virtual laboratories and online videos. While Nigeria faces challenges in infrastructure and ICT facilities, this study leveraged locally available resources such as printed materials and school laboratories. Digital tools like virtual simulations were incorporated only where facilities permitted, ensuring realistic applicability. Open inquiry instructional strategy is an educational technique built on constructivist theories, where students take the lead in their learning by asking their own questions, designing and executing experiments and making conclusions based on their findings. This method promotes student autonomy and involvement, allowing learners to actively participate in the learning process (Onyema, et al., 2019).

Research reveals that open inquiry develops critical thinking, problem-solving, and scientific reasoning skills among students, as they are encouraged to examine issues of personal interest and significance (Owolade, et al., 2022). In open inquiry, students are not passive users of information but active participants in their learning journey. The students begin by posing questions that attract them to investigate further their topic of interest which fosters their curiosity and increases their interests. For example, a student could enquire, "What factors influence the rate of a chemical reaction?" This question serves as a basis for findings, guiding the learner to develop experiments, gather information relevant to their topic of interest, and assess results independently. The function of the teacher in this environment changes from being a major source of knowledge to a facilitator who supports and helps students as they traverse their questions (Wang, et al., 2022).

Furthermore, open inquiry enables students to take charge of their education by independently generating questions, designing experiments, analysing findings and drawing conclusions by leveraging digital resources such as websites, virtual laboratories, online videos, simulations etc. This method contrasts with traditional teacher-centred approaches, which often limit student participation and engagement. In the open inquiry approach, the teacher acts as a facilitator, guiding students through the inquiry process by providing support and scaffolding where needed. This study focused on key chemistry topics such as the concepts of atoms, molecules and ions,

separation technique etc., enabling students to design experiments and analyse results independently. Constructivist principles were applied by designing activities that required students to build on their prior knowledge, engage in problem-solving, and connect theoretical concepts to real-world applications during the inquiry process.

Onyema et al. (2019) highlighted that students using open inquiry demonstrated better understanding and significantly improved academic achievement compared to those taught using traditional methods. Similarly, Owolade et al. (2022) concluded that open inquiry is effective in fostering deeper learning and higher test scores, particularly in secondary school chemistry. The results of these studies indicate that open inquiry is a powerful strategy for improving students' academic achievement, particularly in chemistry as it gives students autonomy to leverage online resources that will help them become independent learners.

The constructivist theory, championed by scholars such as Piaget and Vygotsky, underpins the open inquiry instructional strategy. This theory posits that students actively construct their knowledge through experience and interaction with their environment. Open inquiry aligns with this perspective by encouraging learners to engage in self-directed exploration, which directly enhances their academic performance. By building on prior knowledge and applying new information to solve real-world problems, students develop a robust understanding of scientific concepts (Piaget, 1952; Vygotsky, 1978). The teacher's role in this framework transitions from being the sole provider of knowledge to a facilitator, guiding students' inquiries and supporting their learning journey.

Empirical evidence strongly supports the effectiveness of open inquiry in improving academic achievement. Onyema et al. (2019) reported that chemistry students who participated in open inquiry lessons performed significantly better in post-tests compared to their peers taught using the conventional lecture method. This finding aligns with Owolade et al. (2022), who observed that open inquiry facilitated greater academic gains by encouraging active participation and deeper engagement with the subject matter. These studies confirm that open inquiry is an effective strategy for improving students' test scores and overall academic performance, particularly in science disciplines.

Comparative studies provide further evidence of open inquiry's superiority over traditional methods such as demonstration teaching. Wang et al. (2022) revealed that students taught through open inquiry achieved higher academic outcomes in chemistry assessments compared to those instructed using the demonstration method. This difference can be attributed to the active learning and problem-solving opportunities inherent in open inquiry. While demonstration methods are effective for introducing foundational concepts, they lack the depth and engagement required to achieve sustained academic improvement.

The impact of open inquiry on academic achievement also varies between public and private schools. Research by Anil (2023) and Onyema et al. (2019) highlights that private schools often achieve better results due to advantages such as smaller class sizes, better resources, and more extensive teacher training. In contrast, public schools face challenges like overcrowding and limited facilities, which can hinder the successful implementation of open inquiry. Despite these disparities, studies consistently show that open inquiry improves academic achievement across both school types when adequate support and resources are provided.

While open inquiry has shown promise in fostering engaged learning, its impact on academic achievement in secondary school, particularly in comparison with traditional methods, remains inadequately documented. Despite initial insights into open inquiry's effectiveness across different

school types, most prior research has been constrained by limited sample sizes. Consequently, there is a pressing need for more comprehensive research with larger, more diverse samples to fully understand the potential of open inquiry in varied educational contexts. This study therefore investigated how open inquiry impacts academic achievement in secondary school, comparing it to the demonstration teaching method and assessed differences in outcomes between public and private school students. While resources for open inquiry were limited, the study utilised available laboratory facilities, low-cost teaching aids and information and communication technology tools. Teachers received preliminary training to understand and implement the open inquiry strategy effectively within the constraints of the school environment.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study was to:

1. Assess the impact of open inquiry on secondary school students' academic achievement in chemistry.
2. Compare the academic achievement of students taught using demonstration strategy with those taught using open inquiry.
3. Investigate the difference in the academic achievement between public and private school students taught using open inquiry.

Research Questions

The study answered the following questions:

1. What is the impact of open inquiry on the academic achievement of secondary school students in chemistry?
2. Is there any difference in the academic achievement between students taught using demonstration strategy and those taught using open inquiry?
3. What is the difference in academic achievement between public and private school students taught using open inquiry?

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a non-equivalent pre-test and post-test quasi-experimental research design to evaluate the impact of instructional strategies on students' academic achievement. The experimental group received treatment using the Open Inquiry Instructional Strategy (OIIS), while the control group was taught using the Demonstration Instructional Strategy (DIS). The Quasi-Experimental Design adopted consisted of two groups consisting of six intact classes. The intact classes were created from six purposively selected schools in Osun East Senatorial District. 322 students from the intact classes participated in the study and made up the study's sample size with a total of 166 in the open inquiry and a total of 156 in the demonstration groups.

The groups were categorised according to instructional strategy (Open Inquiry and Demonstration) and school type (Public and Private). The first group, the Experimental Group, were treated with the Open Inquiry Instructional Strategy. These groups included Open Inquiry in Public Schools and Open Inquiry in Private Schools. The second group, the Control Group were treated with the Demonstration Instructional Strategy. These groups included Demonstration in Public Schools and Demonstration in Private Schools. The open inquiry instructional strategy was operationalised through a structured student-centred activities guide (Open Inquiry Instruction Guide, OIIG) where

participants were actively involved in formulating their questions, designing experiments, and independently analyzing results. This approach incorporated locally available laboratory resources, supplemented by virtual tools where feasible, and emphasized self-guided exploration under teacher facilitation.

On the other hand, the demonstration instructional strategy involved teacher-led explanations and demonstrations of experiments following the Demonstration Instruction Guide (DIG). Here, students observed as teachers performed chemical experiments step-by-step, ensuring conceptual clarity and procedural accuracy with minimal student intervention. Both methods adhered to the core chemistry topics of the study, maintaining comparability across the groups. The chemistry teachers in the open inquiry and demonstration groups were trained by the researcher on how to adopt the Open Inquiry Instruction Guide (OIIG) and the Demonstration Instruction Guide (DIG) during the treatment respectively. Additionally, pre-tests and post-tests were conducted using the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) to measure the impact of the treatments on students' academic achievement.

Population and Sample

The target population for the study were senior secondary school students in Osun state while the accessible population consisted of Senior Secondary School Chemistry (SSS1) students in Osun East Senatorial District, Nigeria. These areas are chosen because they represent a broad spectrum of academic backgrounds and experiences with different instructional strategies in chemistry and the study aims to assess the effectiveness of open inquiry and demonstration instructional strategies on students' academic achievement in chemistry in the areas. Using a multi-stage sampling technique, six schools were purposively selected based on the available laboratory facilities, information and communication technology tools and willingness to participate. From these schools, six intact chemistry classes were randomly selected, resulting in 322 students. The classes were assigned to either the experimental or control group using simple random sampling.

Research Instruments

The study employed three key instruments to implement the treatments and evaluate their effectiveness. The Open Inquiry Instruction Guide (OIIG) and Demonstration Instruction Guide (DIG) serve as stimulus instruments and the primary instruments used in the study to standardise how the respective teaching strategies are delivered to participants.

Stimulus Instruments

Open Inquiry Instruction Guide (OIIG): This guide was designed by the researchers to standardise the implementation of the open inquiry instructional strategy. It provided detailed instructions for facilitating student-centred activities, including the formulation of questions, experiment design, and data analysis. The OIIG also included provisions for integrating online videos and simulations for topics without practical experiments, leveraging the school's ICT facilities.

Demonstration Instruction Guide (DIG): This guide was also developed by the researchers to ensure consistency in delivering the demonstration instructional strategy. It outlined step-by-step procedures for teacher-led experiments, followed by student practice under supervision. For non-practical topics, the guide included the use of instructional materials like charts, models, and animations to explain abstract concepts.

Evaluation Instrument

Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT): The CAT was utilised to measure the effectiveness of the instructional strategies on students' academic achievement. The test focused on key chemistry

topics: concepts of atoms, molecules and ions, elements, compounds and mixtures, and separation techniques covered during the four-week intervention. The Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) was adapted from past questions of the West African Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO), and Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB). The CAT consist of two sections. Section A collects demographic data which includes respondents' gender and school type. Section B includes 15 multiple-choice questions, with five questions drawn from each of the three key topics. Each multiple-choice question has one correct answer and three distractors, allowing for an objective assessment of student's academic performance by testing their ability to remember the chemistry concepts covered in the study. The CAT has a maximum score of 30 marks with two marks awarded for each correct answer, and no marks for incorrect answers, ensuring a straightforward grading process.

Validity and Reliability of Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT)

The validity of the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) was established through content validity, ensuring that the items accurately represent the curriculum and concepts covered in the study. The test items were adapted from reputable specifically, past questions from the West African Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO), and Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB). The instrument was thereafter reviewed by the researcher's supervisor to evaluate the relevance and clarity of the questions, ensuring that they accurately measure students' academic achievement.

The reliability of the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) was assessed using the test-retest method. The same test was administered to 50 students at two different points in time, and the correlation between the scores from both administrations was analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient. The results showed a strong positive correlation of 0.863, significant at the 0.05 level ($p < 0.05$), indicating a high degree of stability in the test scores over time. This suggests that the CAT is a reliable tool for measuring students' academic achievement in chemistry.

Research Procedure/Intervention Process

The study was conducted in three phases:

1. **Pre-Treatment Phase:** This phase involved obtaining permissions from the school principals and administering the CAT pre-test to both groups to establish baseline academic achievement.
2. **Treatment Phase:** In this phase, students belonging to the Experimental group were taught using the Open Inquiry Instruction Guide (OIIG) while instructions were delivered to students in the control group through the Demonstration Instruction Guide (DIG). Both groups were taught the topics: concepts of atoms, molecules and ions, elements, compounds and mixtures and separation techniques.

Open Inquiry Instruction Treatment

The open inquiry instructional treatment spanned four weeks, with three 40-minute sessions per week using the Open Inquiry Instruction Guide (OIIG). For topics requiring practicals, students independently formulated research questions, designed experiments and analysed results using available laboratory resources. For example, in separation techniques, students investigated how various methods like filtration and distillation could be applied to purify mixtures.

For topics that did not involve practical experiments (e.g., concepts of atoms and molecules), students accessed online videos, simulations, and other digital resources in the school's computer laboratory. These tools provided a virtual, interactive learning environment where students could visualise abstract concepts like atomic structure and molecular interactions. The teacher acted as

a facilitator, providing guidance and scaffolding, ensuring students understood the steps for engaging with the digital resources, and promoting critical thinking throughout the process.

Demonstration Instruction Treatment

The demonstration treatment also ran for four weeks, with three 40-minute sessions per week, covering the same topics for consistency using the Demonstration Instruction Guide (DIG). For practical topics, teachers demonstrated experiments such as separation techniques using distillation and filtration. Students then practised these methods in small groups, replicating the demonstrated steps under close supervision ensuring safety and precision.

For theoretical topics (e.g., concepts of atoms and molecules), the teacher employed instructional materials such as charts, models, and animations. These tools were used to explain abstract concepts, like the structure of atoms and the formation of compounds, in a step-by-step manner. The teacher engaged students through guided questioning and reinforced their understanding through follow-up discussions.

3. **Post-Treatment Phase:** After the treatment phase, a post-test was done by administering the CAT to both the Experimental and Control Groups to assess academic achievement following the intervention.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 27.0). Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to compare the academic achievement of students taught using demonstration and open inquiry instructional strategies while controlling for pre-test scores as covariates. This method accounted for baseline differences and isolated the effects of the instructional strategies on the post-test academic achievement between students taught using demonstration and open inquiry instructional strategies while controlling for pre-test scores as covariates. Additionally, a Two-Way ANOVA was utilised to compare public and private school students taught using open inquiry. This allowed for the examination of interaction effects between school type and students' academic achievement. The analyses were conducted at a significance level of $p < 0.05$, ensuring the reliability and validity of the results.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the impact of open inquiry on the academic achievement of secondary school students in chemistry?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for the CAT Post-test Scores of Students in the Study Area Based on the Instructional Strategy

Descriptive Statistics			
Dependent Variable: CAT Post-test Score			
Instructional Strategies	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Demonstration	13.21	5.535	156
Open Inquiry	17.53	8.998	166
Total	15.43	7.817	322

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the CAT post-test scores based on open inquiry instructional strategy. Students in the Demonstration group have a mean score of 13.21 with a standard deviation of 5.535, while students in the Open Inquiry group have a mean score of 17.53 with a standard deviation of 8.998. The overall mean for all students is 15.43 with a standard deviation of 7.817. This suggests that students taught using open inquiry scored higher in the post-test than those taught using the demonstration strategy indicating that open inquiry improved the students' academic achievement.

Research Question 2: Is there any difference in the academic achievement between students taught using demonstration strategy and those taught using open inquiry?

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance on the Difference in Academic Achievement of Students in the Study Area

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: CAT Post-test Score						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2879.021 ^a	2	1439.510	27.441	.000	.147
Intercept	6298.030	1	6298.030	120.058	.000	.273
Pre_Test_CAT_Score	1374.676	1	1374.676	26.205	.000	.076
Instructional_Strategy	1504.224	1	1504.224	28.675	.000	.082
Error	16734.110	319	52.458			
Total	96324.000	322				
Corrected Total	19613.130	321				

a. R Squared = .147 (Adjusted R Squared = .141)

Table 2 shows the results of the ANCOVA analysis testing the difference in academic achievement (measured by CAT post-test scores) between students taught using the Demonstration and Open Inquiry instructional strategies. The instructional strategy variable is statistically significant ($F = 28.675, p = 0.000$), indicating a significant difference in academic achievement between the two groups. This suggests that the Open Inquiry strategy had a positive effect on the academic achievement of students when compared to the Demonstration strategy. The partial eta squared value of 0.082 indicates a moderate effect size, meaning that approximately 8.2% of the variance in academic achievement can be attributed to the type of instructional strategy used.

Research Question 3: What is the difference in academic achievement between public and private school students taught using open inquiry?

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance on the Difference in Academic Achievement of Public and Private School Students in the Study Area**Tests of Between-Subjects Effects**

Dependent Variable:							
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	
Corrected Model	1981.907 ^a	3	660.636	11.915	0.000	0.101	
Intercept	44646.061	1	44646.061	805.245	0.000	0.717	
School_Type	385.425	1	385.425	6.952	0.009	0.021	
Inquiry Instructional Strategy	927.072	1	927.072	16.721	0.000	0.050	
School_Type * Open Inquiry Instructional Strategy	31.438	1	31.438	0.567	0.452	0.002	
Error	17631.223	318	55.444				
Total	96324.000	322					
Corrected Total	19613.130	321					

a. R Squared = .101 (Adjusted R Squared = .093)

The results of the Two-Way ANOVA in Table 3 show a statistically significant difference in academic achievement between public and private school students taught using open inquiry ($F(1, 318) = 6.952, p = 0.009, \text{partial eta squared} = 0.021$). This indicates that school type accounts for approximately 2.1% of the variance in post-test scores, with private school students likely outperforming their public school counterparts. Furthermore, the effect of the open inquiry instructional strategy itself is significant ($F(1, 318) = 16.721, p = 0.000, \text{partial eta squared} = 0.050$), showing that the strategy positively impacts academic achievement. However, the interaction between school type and open inquiry (School_Type * Open Inquiry Instructional Strategy) is not significant ($F(1, 318) = 0.567, p = 0.452, \text{partial eta squared} = 0.002$). This implies that while school type influences academic achievement, the effectiveness of open inquiry does not differ significantly between public and private schools.

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed that open inquiry significantly improved students' academic achievement compared to the demonstration method, as evidenced by higher post-test scores among students in the open inquiry group. This result supports Onyema et al. (2019) and Owolade et al. (2022), who found that open inquiry enhances students' understanding and fosters critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The constructivist principles underlying open inquiry, as posited by Piaget

and Vygotsky, are evident in these outcomes, as the strategy promotes active participation and deep engagement with learning materials.

The study also identified significant differences in academic achievement between public and private school students taught using open inquiry, with private school students achieving higher scores. This finding is consistent with Anil (2023) and Onyema et al. (2019), who noted that factors such as smaller class sizes, better resources, and enhanced teacher training in private schools contribute to better academic performance. However, the non-significant interaction between school type and open inquiry suggests that the strategy is equally effective across both school settings, provided adequate resources and support are in place.

These findings emphasize the potential of open inquiry to address the limitations of traditional instructional methods, particularly in science education, where critical thinking and inquiry skills are paramount. The study contributes to the growing body of evidence that open inquiry not only improves academic achievement but also bridges gaps in educational outcomes across different school types when appropriately implemented.

Summary

This study investigated the impact of the Open Inquiry Instructional Strategy on the academic achievement of secondary school students in chemistry, compared to the Demonstration Instructional Strategy. It also examined differences in academic achievement between public and private school students taught using open inquiry. The study used a quasi-experimental design, with pre-test and post-test assessments to measure students' academic performance. The findings showed that students taught using open inquiry outperformed those taught using demonstration, confirming the effectiveness of open inquiry in enhancing academic achievement. Additionally, private school students demonstrated higher achievement levels than public school students, although the effectiveness of open inquiry was found to be consistent across both public and private school settings.

Conclusion

The findings of this study strongly support the efficacy of the Open Inquiry Instructional Strategy in improving secondary school students' academic achievement in chemistry. Open inquiry fosters active learning, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, which are essential for mastering scientific concepts. The study's results align with existing literature that highlights the advantages of student-centred learning approaches over traditional, teacher-centred methods.

However, the study also revealed a significant gap between public and private school students, with private school students achieving better results. This disparity can likely be attributed to differences in resources, teacher training, and class size. Despite this, the consistent effectiveness of open inquiry across both school types suggests that, when implemented properly, open inquiry can help bridge academic gaps and improve student outcomes, regardless of school setting.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Promote Open Inquiry:** Schools, particularly those in public sectors, should adopt open inquiry as an instructional strategy to improve student engagement and achievement in science subjects like chemistry. Training teachers to effectively implement open inquiry strategies can help maximize its potential.

2. **Address Resource Disparities:** Efforts should be made to address the resource gaps between public and private schools. This includes providing adequate digital tools, lab facilities, and professional development opportunities for teachers to support inquiry-based learning.
3. **Further Research:** Future studies should explore the long-term impact of open inquiry on other subjects and include a broader sample size to validate these findings. Additionally, investigating the specific challenges faced by public schools in implementing open inquiry could provide valuable insights for improving educational practices.

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